

ASP 693 CHEERS

“Cultural HEritagE. Risks and Securing activities”

Activity A.T4.1 Emergency Planning and cultural heritages protection: how do the Alps deal with this issue?

An investigation aimed at making a critical comparison of the Emergency Planning regulations in the Alps (roles, responsibilities, involved bodies and subjects), with a in depth analysis of the different schemes applied by competent authorities and Civil Protection bodies in the field of cultural heritage protection against natural hazards

Deliverable D.T2.2.1 Critical overview of Emergency Planning schemes at Alpine level

An overall picture of the different schemes applied at country level, with the synthesis of final recommendations for policy makers

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List of acronyms

DDPS - *Federal Department of Defence, Civil Protection and Sport*

FOCP - Federal Office of Civil Protection

FOEN - Federal Office for the Environment

IRM - Integrated Risk Management

NEOC - National Emergency Operations Centre

PCP - Protection of Cultural Properties

Switzerland

Overview of civil protection system

a) Relevant elements of the administrative structure of the Switzerland

Switzerland is a federal government and the power is divided between the Confederation, the cantons and the municipalities. All levels are involved in the protection of cultural property (PCP).

b) Organization of the civil protection in Switzerland

Civil protection in Switzerland is an organization based on the militia principle and contributes to national security without combat tasks. It was established in 1959 with the vote in favor of the Swiss people on the constitutional article on civil protection and with the first federal law of 1963¹. The Federal Office for Civil Protection (FOCP) is set up at the Federal Department of Defence, Civil Protection and Sport (DDPS).

The organization of civil protection in Switzerland has a federalist structure: the Swiss cantons have the responsibility and competence for civil protection; the confederation - with the Federal Office for Civil Protection (FOCP) - provides a common basis. FOCP is divided in six organizational units: Civil Protection, Spiez Laboratory, National Emergency Operations Centre (NEOC), Training, Telematics and Resources (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1 The organization structure of the Federal Office of Civil Protection (FOCP)

Civil protection is made up of professionals and soldiers. It is based on the system of compulsory service pursuant to the Federal Constitution (as an alternative of the military or civilian service): all men of Swiss citizenship are obliged to provide service by the

¹ The history of civil protection in Switzerland. Website of the Federal Office for Civil Protection <https://www.babs.admin.ch/it/zs/hist.htm>

confederation for a total of 245 days without exceeding a total of 66 days per year per soldier (14 years in total).

c) Scopes of action of civil protection

The scope of civil protection is to intervene during major events, catastrophes, emergency situations and armed conflicts and it is responsible for protecting the population, assisting people in need of protection, protecting cultural properties, supporting conducting bodies and other partner organisations as well as carrying out rehabilitation and utility work². Together with the police, fire brigade, public health services and technical services, it is a partner of the integrated population protection system³. Civil protection, like the other organizations belonging to the integrated system of the protection of the population, designates a cantonal and municipal (or regional) organ of conduct to assess the risks and dangers as well as to delegate planning, preparations and coordination of any intervention by partner organizations. It takes over the conduct of operations in the event of disasters and emergency situations involving several partner organizations (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2 Organization structure of the civil protection

Among the purposes of civil protection there is also the protection of cultural properties (PCP), to which a specific section of the civil protection is dedicated.

At the Confederation level, the section PCP is the competent authority in charge of the protection of cultural property within the FOCP. In addition, an advisory body committee - the Federal Committee for the Protection of Cultural Property - acts as the link between the cultural heritage sector and the civil protection and it is responsible to update the inventory PBC with objects of national and regional importance.

At the Cantonal level, the designated competent authority (in case of Canton Ticino, the Department of the Territory, Office of Cultural Heritage⁴) is responsible for the implementation of protective measures and to contribute financially to the protection of cultural property where responsibility does not lie directly with the Confederation. It is supported by the Department of Civil Protection and Defence especially in the training of

² The Federal Law on Civil Protection includes the protection of cultural property among the tasks of civil protection (Article 28 LPPC; 520.1).

³ Federal Act on Civil Protection and Civil Defence (LPPC; 520.1) of 2019
<https://www.admin.ch/opc/it/classified-compilation/20011872/index.html>

⁴ Dipartimento del territorio, Ufficio dei beni culturali: <https://www4.ti.ch/dt/dstm/sst/ubc/ufficio/>

PCP Militia. In the municipalities and regions, the tasks of the PCP are carried out by personnel incorporated in the civil protection organizations and specially trained (Fig. 2) collaborating with public and private institutions (Fig. 3).

Fig. 3 The structure of the protection of cultural properties (PCP) in Switzerland. Translation from © BABS KGS (2016/2020)⁵

d) Reference methods to set up the emergency response

The integrated risk management approach

The reference model employed by FOCP to cope with catastrophes and emergencies is the Integrated Risk Management (IRM) (Fig. 4). IRM is a systematic process for the comprehensive treatment of risks which aims at reducing the damage extent of natural hazards and the area's vulnerability and to protect people and their livelihoods. Within the FOCP the identification and assessment of hazards, the hazard and risk analyses and an integrated risk management approach are among the main tasks of the civil protection department to prevent, respond and recover potential damages.

A fundamental inventory for the integrated risk management for the civil protection is the “Hazard Catalogue: A Basis for Hazard and Risk Analyses”, a list of natural, technological

⁵ Stratégie PBC 2021-2025: Prévention/Préparation - Intervention - Réhabilitation

and societal hazards which could potentially damage the country or which could have serious repercussions for Switzerland⁶.

Fig. 4 Model Integrated Risk Management. Federal Office for Civil Protection (FOCP), 2019

The integrated risk management has an holistic approach and it merges and combines the ISO 31000 risk management process (Fig. 5) with integrated action planning and participation at different levels. It can be divided in two parts:

1. The integrated hazard analysis and risk assessment (inner circle)
2. The Integrated action planning and implementation (external circle)

The integrated hazard analysis and risk assessment (inner circle) refers to the established risk management process (Fig. 5) allowing a comprehensive treatment of risks. Risk management is at the center of the integrated model approach and it includes risk

⁶ Federal Office for Civil Protection. 2019): Catalogo dei pericoli. Catastrofi e situazioni d'emergenza in Svizzera. 2ª edizione. UFPP, Berna.

identification, risk analysis, risk evaluation and risk assessment as well as communication and consultation and monitoring and review measures.

IRM process as described in ISO 31000

Fig. 5 Integrated Risk Management Process as described in ISO 31000

The integrated risk management follows the subsidiary principle and it is grounded on three main cornerstones of risk treatment: preparedness, response and recovery, which define the integrated action planning and related implementation measures (external circle). Since the boundaries between preparedness, response and recovery measures are fluid where the actual measures themselves are concerned, seven more detailed sub-domains are set out. These are prevention, emergency provisions, preparations for intervention, intervention, recondition, event analysis, and recon-struction.

Prevention measures serve primarily to reduce vulnerability before an event has occurred, or to reduce the magnitude of that event. These are: Legal requirements, Land use planning, Construction / technical measures, Biological measures, Organisational measures.

Emergency provisions serve to prepare the response to disasters and emergency situations. They do not take effect until the damaging event is actually taking place, or thereafter. Emergency plans are the key output of provision planning. The measures of the emergency provision include: Management, Warning and alert systems, Resources for intervention, Emergency planning, Training and exercises, Individual preparations and insurance

Preparations for intervention Preparation measures for intervention are put into action (shortly) before an event occurs. These preparations must also have been laid down in advance in the relevant emergency plans. The measures of the preparation for intervention: early warning and recommendations on appropriate conduct, Increased readiness for intervention,

Intervention. Intervention measures are deployed once an event has occurred. They include immediate action to protect and to rescue individuals, animals and both tangible and intangible assets and to limit damages that as far as possible must be included in the emergency plans. The measures of intervention are: alerts and instructions on appropriate conduct, rescue, damage mitigation, emergency measures / emergency operation

Recondition. Reconditioning means quick-ly setting up provisional solutions, designing essential facilities and transport routes up and running again as quickly as possible. The measures of reconditioning are: Buildings / facilities / businesses, Energy supply, Communication systems, Transport systems, Supplies and utilities / waste disposal

Event analysis is important for the lessons which can be learned and then applied to the reconstruction phase and to future planning. The measures of event analysis: Documentation of the event and lessons for preparedness, response and recovery (e.g. highlight room for improvement; reduce the vulnerability of buildings and infrastructures and apply stricter building standards and planning requirements to properties in risk areas; review the activities of emergency management bodies and emergency teams, and propose improvements)

Reconstruction. The elements of reconstruction are: buildings / facilities / businesses, Reconstruction and strengthening resilience, Financing of reconstruction

Protection of Cultural Property (PCP) Strategy 2021-2025⁷

Recently, within the framework of the PCP Strategy 2021-2025, new considerations for day-to-day risk management in heritage institutions were clarified. The PCP Strategy makes it possible to integrate contingency planning hitherto adopted by cultural institutions into a much broader framework, based on the risk and hazard management developed by the FOCP. Accordingly, the PCP strategy proposes a three-step approach similar to the risk and hazard management (Fig. 6):

- Prevention/Preparedness
- Intervention
- Restoration

⁷ Gérer le risque au quotidien dans les institutions patrimoniales. Stratégie PBC 2021-2025: Prévention/Préparation - Intervention - Réhabilitation, Office fédéral de la protection de la population OFPP, Section Protection des biens culturels PBC, août 2020

Fig. 6 Risk and hazard management model at PBC

From the side of cultural institutions the new strategy stress the need to integrate the different organizational partners of the integrated population protection system - civil protection, police, fire brigade, public health services and technical services - in their risk management system in order to prepare an efficient protection plan (Fig. 7)

Fig. 7 Structure of different partners that should be integrated within the cultural institution risk management system @BABS KGS (2020)

e) Early-warning systems

Federal agencies monitor natural hazards and are responsible for alerting the authorities and population. The offices and agencies and their respective responsibility areas are as follows:

- Dangerous weather conditions: Federal Office for Meteorology and Climatology (MeteoSwiss)
- Floods and associated mud and landslides: Federal Office for the Environment (FOEN)
- Forest fires: Federal Office for the Environment (FOEN)
- Avalanches: Swiss Federal Institute for Forest, Snow and Landscape Research (WSL) Institute for Snow and Avalanche Research (SLF)
- Earthquake alerts: Swiss Seismological Service (SED) at the Federal Institute of Technology (ETH) Zurich

The natural hazard portal⁸ publishes the real-time situation of natural danger monitoring in Switzerland. Federal offices and specialist agencies take a coordinated approach when issuing warnings, and use a scale of 1 to 5 to define the danger category of each danger warning instance.

⁸ Link to the natural hazard portal: <https://www.natural-hazards.ch/home.html?tab=actualdanger>

They communicate the alert to the National Emergency Operations Centre (NEOC) of the FOCP, acting as an hub for rapid, reliable and coordinated communication of warnings from the specialist agencies to the media stations and for ensuring that the warnings issued to the public are coordinated, in terms of content and timing, with those issued to the authorities (Federal Offices/Cantons). NEOC is the body in charge of taking the necessary emergency measures until the FOCP is operational (Art. 7 para. 2). FOCP is responsible for alarm and information systems alerting the authorities and the population, and informing them in the event of imminent danger and in the event of an incident. It manages the warning system for the population, the dissemination of information and instructions on how to behave, an emergency radio channel, and it ensures that the warning is also accessible to people with disabilities⁹.

In collaboration with the federal government, the cantons ensure that the competent bodies are alerted and that the population is informed in the event of an incident. Cantons also regulate the procedure for calling civil protection militia into service in case of emergencies. In the event of severe weather, the relevant cantonal and/or communal authorities are responsible for communicating definite instructions to the public and giving advice on what action to take.¹⁰

f) Human resources involved in the civil protection system

The organization structure of the civil protection is organized based on the military principle in¹¹:

1. Cadres. They refer to the function of :
 - Commander of civil protection (colonel, lieutenant colonel, major, captain)
 - Substitute civil protection commander (major, captain, first lieutenant)
 - Chief situation analysis (first lieutenant, lieutenant)
 - Chief Telematics
 - Chief ABC Protection
 - Chief Logistic Coordination
 - Chief Cultural Heritage Protection
 - Head of Assistance Section
 - Head of Support Section
 - Head of Logistics Element (sergeant major)
 - Accounting and financial management officer (paymaster)
 - Head of telematics team (sergeant, corporal)
 - Head of Assistance Team
 - Head of Health Service Team
 - head of support team
 - Kitchen manager
2. Specialists. They refer to the function of :
 - researcher A (corporal, soldier)
 - person competent in radiation protection

⁹ Art.9 of the Federal Act on Civil Protection and Civil Defence (LPPC; 520.1).

<https://www.fedlex.admin.ch/eli/cc/2020/887/it>

¹⁰ Alerting and informing. Issuing natural danger warnings to the public. Website of the Federal Office for Civil Protection FOCP. <https://www.babs.admin.ch/en/alarm/warning.html>

¹¹ Ufficio Federale della protezione della Popolazione. 2015. La protezione civile. Base. Missione, intervento

- emergency medical aid officer
 - PCP specialist
 - rescuer
 - driver
3. Troops (soldiers) They refer to the function of :
- assistant of staff
 - assistance officer
 - pioneer
 - plant supervisor
 - equipment supervisor
 - chef

Emergency planning instruments and Cultural Heritage safeguarding

Emergency Planning & Response

a) Emergency planning instruments

Protective measures for cultural property

The main regulation for the civil protection is the Federal Act on Civil Protection and Civil Defence (LPPC; 520.1) of 2019, according to which each cantons approves its specific law. In the case of the protection of cultural properties, the above mentioned law is directly connected with the Federal Act on the Protection of Cultural Property in the Event of Armed Conflict, Disaster and Emergency Situations (LPBC; RS 520.3)¹² and the related Ordinance (OPBC: RS 520.31)¹³. These are the federal guideline setting the responsibilities of the confederation, cantons, municipalities and cultural institutions and the related measures to adopt for preventing the lost of cultural properties and facilitating the rescue activities:

- inventories (Confederation, cantons, municipalities),
- security documentation and microfilms, (cantons)
- brief documentation (municipalities)
- shelters, secure storage (Confederation, cantons, municipalities)
- identification of cultural property
- organisation / staff training
- information and awareness-raising
- basic research

¹² Legge federale sulla protezione dei beni culturali in caso di conflitti armati, catastrofi e situazioni d'emergenza del 20 giugno 2014 (LPBC; RS 520.3)

¹³ Ordinanza sulla protezione dei beni culturali in caso di conflitti armati, catastrofi e situazioni d'emergenza (OPBC: RS 520.31) del 29 ottobre 2014

Table 1 Responsibilities and measures of the Swiss federal government for the PCP

Confederation	Cantons	Municipalities
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Assisting and supporting the cantons in implementing the prescribed measures ● issuing instructions and directives ● instructing senior PCP staff in the field of civil protection and the staff of cultural institutions ● helping to compile security documentation ● purchasing and storing microfilms and photographic security reproductions ● make contributions to the construction of shelters ● ensuring information and exchange with Swiss and international institutions. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Create the necessary legislative framework at the cantonal level ● Designate an office responsible for the protection of cultural property ● Draw up an inventory of cultural property ● Create documentation for the safeguarding of cultural property ● Determine what form of organisation is required for the protection of cultural property at the local level ● Train the staff responsible for the protection of cultural property ● Plan the building of shelters for the protection of cultural property. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Building of shelters to protect cultural property ● Arranging for suitable staff ● Organising refresher courses for staff involved in the protection of cultural property ● Implementation of the planned measures with due notification.

Guidelines for the preparation of a disaster plan.

The Federal Office for Civil Protection has published guidelines for cultural institutions for the preparation of a disaster plan aimed at preventing the risk of damage of cultural properties and to reduce negative consequences with simple and inexpensive planning and precautionary measures¹⁴. The guidelines (Fig. 6) have the form of a checking list in order to be downloaded and adapted to local requirements. The guidelines aims at help cultural cultural institution to identify measures to be taken before, during and after the event:

1. **Hazard analysis to immovable cultural properties**
2. **Precautionary measures including:**
 - a. List of cultural property to be evacuated
 - b. Safeguard documentation (inventory sheets)

¹⁴ In 2012, FOEC in collaboration with the Library of the University of Basel published the "Guide to drawing up an emergency plan", which refers in particular to the Basel Canton. The document adds to the previous 'Guide to a disaster plan' (1999) which was published in the form of a checklist and that is shows in fig. 3, a reflection about the important collaboration between all the stakeholders involved (cultural institution, civil protection and fire-man) and it focuses on the internal organisational requirements involved in carrying out an emergency plan.

- c. Technical installations and arrangements
 - d. Shelters for cultural property
 - e. Staff briefing and training
 - f. Other field fundamentals for an emergency plan (detailed plans of buildings, addresses and telephone numbers, Location of keys, access, etc)
3. **Immediate action in case of incidents involving damage.** Depending on the nature of the damage (fire, water damage/flooding, vandalism, theft) the disaster plan include the measures to be taken and the persons and authorities to be notified (tel: home and office)
 4. **Restoration and reconstruction needs after the event** based on the list of inventory and safeguard documentation and the involvement of specialists.
 - 5.

PROTECTION FOR HISTORIC ITEMS AT TIMES OF DISASTER

Hazard Analysis	Precautions (Annexes 1 + 2)	Emergency action (Annex 3)	Restoration / Reconstruction
Identify hazards to immovable historic items, such as: - Fire - Water damage - Flooding - Avalanches - Landslides - Earthquakes - Vandalism - Theft - and so on...	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Check the technical installations from time to time - Be sure to do the following: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Make a list of the items that must be evacuated • Prepare safeguard documentation • Take constructional and technical precautions • Prepare shelters for historic items • Prepare lists with telephone numbers of specialists who must be alerted if there is an incident • Draw up a list of specialists who can be called in if repair or restoration is required - Keep staff informed, trained and exercised <p style="text-align: center; color: white;">↓ DISASTER PLAN</p>	Take steps in accordance with the guidelines ↓ TAKE IMMEDIATE ACTION	Call in specialists to help with restoration The following paperwork will prove useful: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lists, inventories • Safeguard documentation

<
Deployment of the resources of the Heritage Protection Service
>
Specialists
>

Fig. 6 Guidelines for the preparation of a disaster plan.
<https://www.babs.admin.ch/en/aufgabenbabs/kgs/massnahmen.html>

Other relevant guidelines for Protection of Cultural Properties (PCP)

Other relevant but more specific guidelines have been published by the PCP of the Federal Office for Civil Protection (FOCP) in order to help cultural institutions and cantonal authorities to verify the requirements, priorities and recovery interventions of the measures they have to manage for the protection of cultural properties.

1. (in Italian) **Water damage to archives - what to do?** (Guidelines No. 1/2003) .
<https://www.babs.admin.ch/it/aufgabenbabs/kgs/prints.detail.publication.html/babs-internet/it/publications/kgs/guidelines/guidelines1it.pdf.html>
2. (in Italian) **PCP Security Documentation Requirements** (Guidelines 2/2006).
<https://www.babs.admin.ch/it/aufgabenbabs/kgs/prints.detail.publication.html/babs-internet/it/publications/kgs/guidelines/guidelines2it.pdf.html>
3. (in English) **Cultural property shelters: construction of new refuges and repurposing of decommissioned protected facilities** (Guidelines 2020).
<https://www.babs.admin.ch/en/aufgabenbabs/kgs/massnahmen.html>

b) Scopes of action of those instruments

The disaster plan of a cultural institution aims at releasing all the measures adopted in the forecasting and prevention of a natural hazard as well as immediate intervention and recovery activities.

PCP Security Documentation Requirements and the Cultural property shelters guidelines have the scope of preventing damage, the guide “Water damage to archives - what to do?” instead aims at preventing and recovery activity.

c) Emergency planning and cultural heritage safeguarding

All the guidelines presented above deal with the protection of cultural property as they have specifically drawn for the PCP Section, according to the general regulation of civil protection.

Elements for policy recommendations

i) Do the Emergency Planning instruments currently in place at country level address the issue of the safeguarding of cultural heritage? If so, what are the strengths and weaknesses of those planning tools? If not, what is the reason for this gap?

Emergency planning instruments in Switzerland address the issue of the safeguarding of cultural heritage. The integration of risk management within cultural properties could be strengthened by cantons and municipalities.

ii. Does the goal of safeguarding Cultural Heritage require modifications/improvements of the Disaster Management system currently in place (at the different administrative levels)? What modifications/improvements/recommendations are you able to suggest, based on your analysis and experience?

Switzerland has just taken steps in this direction through the 2021-2025 PCP strategy by relating the integrated risk plan with the guidelines for the preparation of an emergency plan. These initiatives have been launched recently and will take time to implement.

iii. During the most recent states of alert or emergency for natural phenomena, has an operational interaction between civil protection and managers of cultural heritage been activated? What areas of improvement could be envisaged in the interactions between the two areas?

The relation and interaction between the civil protection and managers of cultural heritage needs to be better defined. An interaction is necessary between the management of a collection by the museum, the public responsible for the protection of cultural heritage (a cantonal level, the Office of Cultural Heritage) and the civil protection. At the moment the civil protection collaborates with the Office of Cultural Heritage for the inventory of cultural properties and objects, and it releases intervention sheets to be shared with firemen. These sheets indicate which objects have to be saved and their priority. However the documentation is not necessarily shared with cultural heritage managers.

iv. Are the overall capacity (training level) of the civil protection operators and available resources (number of operators) adequate to provide an effective response in the field of safeguarding and securing cultural heritage in crisis situations?

Yes, the training of the civil protection militia in the protection of cultural property is undoubtedly a strong value. At cantonal level since 1993, three 5-day courses have been held every year by each cantons to train civil protection specialists in the protection of cultural properties in emergency situations. These courses cover the following activities: 1) collecting data, 2) handling works of art, 3) preparing protection and evacuation measures, 4) preparing intervention plans; particular emphasis is placed on cataloguing, which is an indispensable basis for any intervention and security measures.

In Canton Ticino, the Office of Cultural Heritage of the Department of the territory is the main consultant of the PCP, it is responsible for cataloguing cultural properties (of national, cantonal and local importance) and for contributing to the training of civil protection specialists in PCP, the drawing up of intervention plans (priorities) and safety documentation. The common objective of this collaboration between the Office of Cultural Heritage and the civil protection is to ensure the highest quality both in the preparatory work (training of soldiers; cataloguing) and in the preparation of the operational phases (intervention, protection and evacuation plans).

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